

A NOTE ON THE LECITHIN CONTENT OF THE BLOOD OF INDIAN WOMEN IN NORMAL CONDITION AND IN PREGNANCY.

BY HEMENDRA NATH CHATTERJEE AND SURATH MOHAN GHOSH.

The lecithin content of the whole blood has been determined by the method of Whitehorn (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1924, 62, 133). The blood was examined in 25 normal non-pregnant women and 25 women in the different terms of pregnancy from fifth month upto nearly the term. The figures in the following table show that there is a distinct rise in the figures for lecithin during pregnancy.

Normal pregnancy.		Normal females.	
Case No.	Amount in mg. per 100 c.c. of blood.	Case No.	Amount in mg. per 100 c.c. of blood
1	13.3	1	9.5
2	12.5	2	9.5
3	13.3	3	9.1
4	11.1	4	10.0
5	10.5	5	6.8 (Lowest)
6	11.1	6	7.4
7	12.5	7	8.7
8	11.1	8	10.0
9	12.5	9	8.7
10	12.5	10	11.1 (Highest).
11	16.6	11	11.1
12	13.3	12	11.1
13	11.1	13	9.5
14	11.2	14	8.7
15	13.3	15	9.5
16	14.2	16	9.5
17	12.5	17	9.5
18	16.2	18	10.0
19	17.0 (Highest)	19	8.3
20	13.3	20	11.1
21	11.5	21	9.0
22	12.5	22	9.5
23	10.5	23	10.0
24	10.0 (Lowest)	24	9.1
25	10.3	25	7.0
Average	12.54	Average	9.34
Standard deviation	± 1.87	Standard deviation	± 1.14

The blood was drawn between 10 and 12 A.M. and on empty stomach.

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DEPARTMENT OF PATHOLOGY,
CARMICHAEL MEDICAL COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

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